

**PROBLEMS OF STYLISTICS OF THE MODERN RUSSIAN
LANGUAGE**

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Annotation. This article is devoted to stylistic norms and problems of typology of speech deviations, about the varieties of lexical and stylistic errors in speech.

Key words: Stylistic norms, academic and colloquial styles of pronunciation, lexical and stylistic errors, stylistic shortcomings, communicative and stylistic errors.

The system of styles of the literary language is formed historically, enriched and complicated in the process of long development. From the standpoint of functional stylistics in the modern Russian literary language, it is customary to distinguish five main styles: scientific, official business, journalistic, colloquial and artistic, or the language of fiction. Of these, the first three styles - scientific, official business and journalistic - are generally recognized. Spoken and artistic still remain problematic and are interpreted differently by linguists. The language of fiction is interpreted by a number of scholars as a special type of literary language. According to N.A. Meshchersky, N.M. Shansky, L.Yu. Maksimov, the use of linguistic means in fiction is determined by its own special aesthetic norms. In the same way, according to some scientists, colloquial speech is a special type of language, since it has its own system of norms, which often does not coincide with the codified norms of the literary language. However, other functional subsystems of the literary language also have their own special norms that determine the selection and use of linguistic means. At the same time, all subsystems of the literary language have common norms. In this regard, it is

customary today to subdivide literary norms into general literary (general language) and stylistic.

Stylistic norms cannot be opposed to literary norms. They are a kind of literary norms, but have their own characteristics. Each style implements, first of all, general language, or interstyle, norms - orthoepic, spelling, lexicophraseological, grammatical (morphological and syntactic). But at the same time, each style has its own functional and style norms, which, on the one hand, concretize general language norms, and on the other hand, expand and enrich them [1].

Thus, taking into account the nature and functional role, all literary norms are usually divided into two categories: general language, general literary norms and stylistic norms. General language, general literary norms regulate the use of national language means in our speech, they indicate the normativity or non-normativity of the means of the national language, their admissibility or inadmissibility in literary speech, establishing a kind of ban on the use of dialectisms, jargon, colloquial words and forms in literary speech. Stylistic norms are also literary norms, but of a special, special purpose. Stylistic norms are associated with the features of the functional styles of the language, they clarify the general literary norms in all those cases when various options are allowed within their limits. Being multi-level, stylistic norms are at the same time multi-layered, since each functional style is implemented in different genre forms, in texts for different purposes. In this regard, among the stylistic norms, the most general ones, characteristic of the functional style as a whole, and private ones, characteristic of individual genres, speech situations, and different types of text, are distinguished. This multi-layered, dynamism of stylistic norms is ultimately determined by the expediency of using language means in one or another speech act (V.G. Kostomarov, A.A. Leontiev, M.N. Kozhina, etc.).

Taking into account the multi-layeredness, stylistic norms can be defined as historically established exemplary ways of using the variable means of the literary

language in different styles, genres, speech situations, in different specific texts.

Indeed, only the lack of an objective scientific study of the use of pronunciation variants in different areas of public speech can explain that the same orthoepic dictionary [2] in similar inflectional paradigms allows individual verbs to have accentological variation. Another thing is that these accentological variants within the same inflectional paradigm can differ stylistically. But in the dictionaries of this flexible system of stylistic characteristics, there are no pronunciation variants yet. Formally, some of the stylistic marks in the introductory articles are declared, but in practice they are almost not used at all.

To date, there is still no single typology of the styles of modern Russian literary pronunciation themselves, on the basis of which a single flexible system of stylistic and orthoepic marks could be formed. R.I. Avanesov in the book "Russian Literary Pronunciation" identified four styles: high, neutral, colloquial and stage. High, colloquial and stage styles are characterized by R.I. Avanesov as expressively colored. In this classification, the allocation of high style is questionable. In modern literary speech, there are pronunciation variants with a high expressive coloring, for example, the pronunciation of the words sonnet, poet, glass in solemn situations without reduction of the pre-stressed vowel sound. But these are just isolated facts that occur mainly in stage pronunciation. As M.N. Nesterov in the article "Typology of styles and stylistic variants of modern Russian literary pronunciation", "it is hardly possible to speak in relation to the literary speech of our century about the high style of pronunciation as a special system of orthoepic means, with a clearly defined scope of use and its own distinctive function. It would be more correct, obviously, to consider high pronunciation not in a number of functional styles, but as a more local phenomenon that characterizes individual genres and situational forms of artistic, less often public speech" [3]. In his opinion, in Russian literary pronunciation of our days, three main pronunciation styles are clearly visible: 1) strict, or academic style of pronunciation, 2) colloquial pronunciation style, 3) stage style, which occupies a special place in the orthoepic

system of the literary language. The academic and colloquial styles of pronunciation clearly correlate with the functional styles of the modern Russian language. Strict, academic pronunciation is typical for scientific, journalistic and official business speech. Colloquial pronunciation characterizes literary and colloquial speech. Stage pronunciation corresponds to the language of fiction. Stage pronunciation performs an aesthetic function. At its core, it is exemplary, academic. But on the stage, for artistic purposes, various pronunciation options are reproduced, both colloquial, folk-poetic, and colloquial, dialect, slang, obsolete. Taking into account the variability of literary pronunciation, it is advisable, in our opinion, to improve the system of stylistic characteristics in orthoepic dictionaries and teaching aids. The system of orthoepic marks should be flexible and stylistically multifaceted. The tag “wrong” should obviously be applied only to actual distortions of words and illiterate speech: anbitia, serious, dilector, bulgahter, etc. The original vernacular and dialectal pronunciation should be accompanied by appropriate characteristics. In school practice, of course, all variants of non-literary pronunciation can be called errors. But there is hardly any good reason to call cases of inappropriate use errors. Stylistic shortcomings often include unmotivated use of colloquial, slang, dialect words in literary speech. Moreover, even in textbooks on functional style: The girl put the child in a shaky place, Pavel rallies his friends even more. At the same time, colloquial inflectional forms qualify as grammatical errors of a non-stylistic type: We want to go to the forest. Such contradictions are due to the lack of a unified approach to distinguishing speech deviations from general literary and stylistic norms. The attribution of unmotivated use of non-literary vocabulary to stylistic errors is due to the fact that in explanatory dictionaries the system of stylistic marks includes not only stylistic marks proper (colloquial, bookish, special, etc.), but also orthological ones: dialect, slang, vernacular. Meanwhile, the latter are only conditionally called stylistic, since they indicate the non-literary sphere of the use of words, and not their attachment to any style of the literary language. Therefore, with a unified

approach to the typology of speech deviations from the norms, the unmotivated use of non-literary vocabulary should, obviously, be attributed to lexical errors, since general literary norms are violated.

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